

graded 1-2. Varieties considered sensitive were graded 4-5.

We submerged detached leaves from Shanyou 63 (a photo-oxidation-sensitive indica hybrid rice) in low CO₂, low O₂ pure water under three light intensities (see figure). Chlorophyll contents under dark, weak light (180 μE/m² per s), and stronger light (600 μE/m² per s) were reduced by 31.4, 50.6, 70.4%, respectively ($[\text{pretreatment} - \text{posttreatment}] / \text{pretreatment} \times 100\%$). Decrease in chlorophyll content was correlated with increase in light intensity, indicating that higher light is a major factor in destroying photosynthetic pigment (especially chlorophyll a).

Chlorophyll content in leaves floating on the water under ambient atmosphere (CO₂ 340 ppm, O₂ 21%) for 6 d decreased by 86.4, 75.0, 88.2%, respectively, for the three intensities. Darkness is a major cause under ambient air conditions of inducing destruction of photosynthetic pigment.

We tested 59 rice germplasm resources at heading stage from different areas and countries for tolerance to photo-oxidation using this technique.

Chlorophyll content (mg/cm²)

Effect of different light intensities on chlorophyll content of excised Shan you 63 leaves (a) immersed in water and (b) floated on water.

Results showed japonica rice as more tolerant than indica (see table).

Leaf color in most indica rices scored 3-5. Indica cultivars BR1083-41-2-4-2-1 and Tian rui 408 were selected as tolerant

of photo-oxidation (grade 2) based on leaf color. Results suggest that pure water and sunlight could be used to accelerate photo-oxidation of rice leaves. □

Stress tolerance—excess water

Effect of submergence on rice yield

R. Rajendran, S. Santhanabosu, P. K. Selvaraj, and V. S. Shanmugasundaram, Soil and Water Management Research Institute (SWMRI), Kattuthottam, Thanjavur 613501, India

Nearly 40,500 ha of rice in the Cauvery Delta of Thanjavur District are submerged up to 1 m or deeper for 8-15 d during the northeast monsoon (Oct-Nov). CR1009 (Ponmani) can withstand inundation better than such varieties as ADT39, IR20, and Co 43.

We conducted experiments in 1988-89 and 1989-90 during samba season (Aug-Jan) at SWMRI to determine the effects of inundation at various growth stages and submergence depths. Plots (40 m²) were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. We transplanted 35-d-old CR1009 at 20- ×

10-cm spacing. Water levels were 25, 50, and 75% of total plant height during maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering. Control plots had 5 cm of water,

Inundation at 25-75% plant height generally significantly reduced grain

yield at all three growth stages. Yields were lowest when the crop was inundated to 75% plant height during flowering.

When flooding occurs during flowering, water should be drained to prevent yield loss. This is nearly impossible, however, in delta coastal areas where incessant monsoon rains usually coincide with vulnerable crop stages. □

Effect of inundation depth at various crop stages on grain yield of CR1009 rice (160 d).

Crop stage	Rice yield (t/ha) at indicated depth of inundation ^a							
	1988-89				1989-90			
	25%	50%	75%	Mean	25%	50%	75%	Mean
Maximum tillering	6.7	5.8	5.7	5.9	6.9	6.6	6.6	6.7
Panicle initiation	6.1	5.9	5.5	5.8	6.6	6.3	5.8	6.2
Flowering	5.8	5.2	3.2	4.7	6.4	6.1	4.4	5.6
Control (5cm water after depletion)	—	—	—	7.6	—	—	—	7.7
Mean	6.0	5.6	4.8	—	6.1	6.3	5.6	—
Depth or stage:	SE ± 0.2			—	SE ± 0.0			—
	LSD (0.05) 0.7			—	LSD (0.05) 0.2			—
Interaction	SE ± 0.4			—	SE ± 0.1			—
	LSD (0.05) 1.2			—	LSD (0.05) 0.3			—

^aInundation depth is expressed as percent of plant height.